

Happy Employees are Productive Employees - An Empirical Study

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Introduction :

Job Satisfaction perhaps the major area where academicians are trying to define, identity and measure the industrialists are seeking it and government is enthusiastically supporting it.

Job satisfaction - or lack of it - hinges on a productive, accomplishing relationship between staff and management; indeed, the success of any organization depends on staff members who enjoy their jobs and feel rewarded by their efforts. Ultimately, of all the people in the marketplace may suffer the most when this vital success factor is lacking. In earlier ages, many researchers have been directed on job satisfaction but this still remains an issue for many organizations. The ambition of this research paper is to examine the satisfaction level of the employees and helps organizations to know about the elements that influence job satisfaction.

Importance of Job Satisfaction :

Job satisfaction is a frequently studied subject in work and organizational literature. This is mainly due to the fact that many experts believe that job satisfaction trends can affect labour market behaviour and influence work productivity, work effort, employee absenteeism and staff turnover. Moreover, job satisfaction is considered a strong predictor of overall individual well-being, as well as a good predictor of intentions or decisions of employees to leave a job.

Job satisfaction is also important in everyday life. Organizations have significant effects on the people who work for them and some of those effects are reflected in how people feel about their work. This makes job satisfaction an issue of substantial importance for both employers and employees.

As many studies suggest, employers benefit from satisfied employees as they are more likely to profit from lower staff turnover and higher productivity if their employees experience a high level of job satisfaction. However, employees should also '*be happy in their work, given the amount of time they have to devote to it throughout their working lives*'.

Factors affecting Job Satisfaction :

Job satisfaction refers to a general attitude which an employee retains on account of many specific attitudes in the following areas :

➤ Personal Factors :

They include workers' sex, education, age, marital status and their personal characteristics, family background, socio-economic background and the like.

➤ Factors Inherent in the Job :

These factors have recently been studied and found to be important in the selection of employees. Instead of being guided by their co-workers and supervisors, the skilled workers would rather like to be guided by their own inclination to choose jobs in consideration of '*what they have to do*'. These factors include- the work itself, conditions, influence of internal and external environment on the job which are uncontrolled by the management, etc.

➤ Factors Controlled by the Management :

The nature of supervision, job security, kind of work group, and wage rate, promotional opportunities, and transfer policy, duration of work and sense of responsibilities are factors controlled by management. All these factors greatly influence the workers. These factors motivate the workers and provide a sense of job satisfaction.

Relations with some variables are given below :

➤ **Job Satisfaction and Turnover :**

Job satisfaction consistently correlates with turnover. It might have been seen that employees having low job-satisfaction leave their employer as early as possible. So, low job satisfaction increases the turnover and high job satisfaction decreases it. Thus it has a negative correlation with labour turnover.

➤ **Job Satisfaction and Absenteeism :**

Absenteeism has the same relationship with the job satisfaction as has the turnover. Both are negatively correlated. Employees who have low job satisfaction tend to remain absent off and on from their job.

➤ **Job Satisfaction and Community Condition :**

Job satisfaction is influenced by community conditions. It is generally advocated that poor community conditions pull down job satisfaction and better community conditions push it up. But this is not always true. What usually happens is that employees compare their community conditions with their job conditions. If job conditions are better than that of community conditions, job satisfaction is higher.

Most usually, workers compare job's '*way of life*' with the community way of living and they are more satisfied when these two values come reasonably close together. If job's way of life is better than the community way of life, job satisfaction is higher and if job's way of life is worse than the community way of living, job satisfaction will be lower.

➤ **Job Satisfaction and Productivity :**

Based on research carried out in Hawthorne studies, further research to prove that "*happy workers are productive*" was carried out, which has been proved negative. Based on the conclusion of Hawthorne studies, managers began their efforts to make their employees happier by improving work conditions, providing Laissez-faire type of leadership, expanding various facilities to the workers, but it has been found that there is no direct relationship between happiness and productivity.

Conclusion :

Job satisfaction is a motivation factor as well as an integration factor. High job satisfaction contributes to organizational commitment, job involvement, better physical and mental health and quality life to the employees. On the other hand, job dissatisfaction leads to absenteeism, labour turnover and labour problems and a negative organizational climate.

References :

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